

ISSUES OF IMPROVING LEGISLATION ON THE PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF ENTREPRENEURS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The Republic was only able to advance along the path of regeneration and progress by fostering a welcoming business environment and developing a successful system for achieving the interests of each citizen. In this way, the development of small businesses, which will saturate the domestic market with the necessary consumer goods and services, generate new employment opportunities, and produce goods that are competitive in international markets, is closely related to the direction of the market and the transformation of the economy in Uzbekistan.

A variety of ownership structures is the primary requirement for the successful development of market relations and stabilization of the Republic's economy. Fundamental adjustments in the overall ownership structure and methods of its implementation were necessary for the economic system to evolve and move toward a market economy. The Republic was only able to advance along the path of regeneration and progress by fostering a welcoming business environment and developing a successful system for achieving the interests of each citizen. In this way, the development of small businesses, which will saturate the domestic market with the necessary consumer goods and services, generate new employment opportunities, and produce goods that are competitive in international markets, is closely related to the direction of the market and the transformation of the economy in Uzbekistan.

Numerous structural actions were made in 2016–2018 with the goal of fostering business environments and luring foreign investment for small and private firms, which form the backbone of Uzbekistan's developing economy. In order to promote faster development of entrepreneurship, complete protection of private property, and qualitative improvement of the business climate, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyeva, issued a decree in October 2016. The "On Additional Measures to Improve the Mechanisms for Providing Public Services to Business Entities" Presidential Decree was adopted on February 1st, 2017 in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Both of these documents aim to enhance the business environment by getting rid of all sorts of unauthorized, counterinspections, and barriers.

Special attention is paid to the adoption of robust policies that ensure the dynamic modernization of small and private businesses and foster their export-related activities, which ought to be the main focus of economic growth for the development of industries and regions and ensure employment for the populace. Additional policies that support exporting by small firms and private enterprise are also under consideration.

All business businesses, with the exception of banks, credit bureaus, and their branches and representative offices, must register with the state through the "one window" facilities. This

bill seeks to establish a single system for state registration and business entity registration in place of the current disjointed one. The sector had rapid expansion in 2016–2017, which was largely due to the efficient execution of measures to ensure the reliable protection of private property and small company interests.

Over the course of the year, the contribution of small business goods to the country's overall gross domestic product rose. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Additional Measures to Ensure Accelerated Development of Entrepreneurial Activity, Full Protection of Private Property and Qualitative Improvement of the Business Climate" from January 1, 2017, all forms of unscheduled inspections of the operations of business entities were canceled, with the exception of inspections in connection with the liquidation of a legal entity, as well as conducted exclusively by authorized government officials. Additionally, this agreement eliminated any and all counter inspections of the operations of commercial companies, including those in illegal circumstances. The following portions of the Decree represent important initiatives to promote entrepreneurship:

1. the application of penalties and financial sanctions (aside from penalties) for business entities and their employees who have violated the law for the first time while engaging in financial and economic activities, in the event that violations are voluntarily eliminated within the time limits established by law, and compensation for material damage caused, excluding cases of harm to human life and health.
2. Exemption from administrative and criminal liability for those who have first-time violations involving the implementation of illegal business activities in exchange for voluntary compensation for harm done, business entity registration, and registration of required permits within one month of the offense's discovery;
3. Business entities who apply for the issuing of a writ of execution for the enforcement of arbitration court decisions are free from paying state taxes;
4. Refusal to impose a criminal penalty that would deny someone the ability to run a business with a connection to other business organizations.

A presidential decree No.2646¹ was adopted on October 28, 2016, in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Accordingly, it is intended to enhance the legal and regulatory environment for state registration and corporate entity registration. On October 28, 2016, a decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted №-2646. A few decisions taken by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Republic were deemed invalid in Uzbekistan in line with the document, which also underwent changes and additions. A stamp, a photo card, a copy of a passport, a card for passing the registration (authorization) procedures, a certificate confirming the self-government body of citizens at the place of residence of an individual entrepreneur, a unique login and password confirming the reservation of an available brand name, and other documents and (or) information that are not required.

On August 29, 2017², Uzbekistan's President Shavkat Mirziyoyev established the Presidential Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities Institute. The decision aims to "strengthen guarantees for the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities, prevent unjustified interference of state bodies in their activities, strengthen the legal framework of private property ownership, as well as ensure the principle of priority of business entities' rights."

In order to radically increase the effectiveness of the ongoing reforms, create conditions for ensuring the comprehensive and accelerated development of the state and society, the implementation of priority directions for the modernization of the country, and the Decree of

¹ Collection of Resolutions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017. No. 2. Article 5

² Collection of Resolutions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017. No. 2.

the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was issued, large-scale reforms carried out during the years of independence laid a solid foundation for national statehood and sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, inviolability of state borders, the rule of law, human rights and freedoms, interethnic harmony, and religious tolerance in society created worthy living conditions for the population, and the realization of the creative potential of citizens. Rejecting administrative and command-style economic management, implementing market reforms gradually, and pursuing a balanced monetary policy all helped to ensure macroeconomic stability, high rates of economic growth, and inflation that stayed within expected bounds, as well as open up numerous opportunities and favorable conditions for the growth of small businesses, private enterprise, and the farmer movement. In addition, a thorough examination of the previous stage of the nation's development, the shifting dynamics of the global economy in light of globalization, and the escalating level of competition necessitate the creation and application of fundamentally novel concepts and ideas for the nation's continued, advanced, and sustainable development³.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further reduce and simplify licensing and licensing procedures in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as improve business conditions". In accordance with the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, comprehensive institutional and structural reforms are being implemented in the republic aimed at reducing the state's presence in the economy, further strengthening the protection of the rights of business entities and the priority role private property, comprehensive stimulation of business initiatives and startups. The effectiveness and efficiency of the measures taken to improve the business climate are objectively reflected in the positive assessments of leading international financial organizations and rating agencies. In particular, in the World Bank's Doing Business 2018 report, Uzbekistan entered the top ten reformer countries in the world for creating the most favorable conditions for entrepreneurship.⁴ Simultaneously, there are still bureaucratic methods of government regulation of the business sphere in a number of areas, which prevents the rapid rise in domestic business competitiveness, the introduction of new technologies and innovations in the business environment, and the development of confidence in the consistency of government policy to create a favorable investment climate and business environment.

The Uzbek Republic Law "On Amendments and Additions to the Uzbek Republic Law "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity". The primary goals of this Law are to establish safeguards and conditions for individuals' unrestricted interest in and engagement in entrepreneurial activity, to increase their commercial activity, and to safeguard the rights and legitimate interests of commercial enterprises. Enterprises with foreign investments are also governed by laws on guarantees and measures to protect the rights of foreign investors in relation to guarantees and measures to protect the rights of business entities. As a result, it can be said that Uzbekistan as a whole has developed a favorable economic climate that is governed by the legislative and regulatory framework as well as particularly developed institutions. Simultaneously, as the effects of globalization processes grow, circumstances must be created to further boost domestic producers' competitiveness in both domestic and international commodities markets. In our opinion, it is crucial to pay close attention to entrepreneurs' management skills in order to help them use the available resources as effectively as possible and to encourage the application of innovations in the small business

³ Tkalich Ya.E. The formation of the infrastructure of state credit support for small and medium-sized businesses in Russia // Problems of modern science and education, 2018. No. 2 (122). pp. 29-34

⁴ Толибов И. Ш., Курпаяниди К. И. Рейтинг Всемирного банка DB2018 и его место в разработке дорожной карты развития предпринимательства в Узбекистане // Международный научный обзор проблем экономики и менеджмента. Проблемы науки. Москва, 2018. № 5. С. 21-28

sector.⁵ The analysis of the legislative and regulatory framework reveals that the process of creating a legal framework to support the growth of small businesses in Uzbekistan and their continued collaboration with large corporations is dynamic in nature, with the goal of minimizing the subjective factors that obstruct the formation of a class of real owners.

Improving tax administration and aligning tax policy with global norms are necessary to increase the effectiveness of the state finance function in the Republic of Uzbekistan. After all, the state's ability to finance itself depends on the adequacy of its budgetary revenues. The coordination of prompt payment of taxes and fees to the budget is the primary responsibility of tax administration. The institution-tax audits in this procedure, which demand the establishment of a direct interaction with taxpayers, are given special consideration. The tax authority will have access to the taxpayer's rights, interests, property, territory, premises, goods, work, services, and funds in the bank account during the tax audit procedure from a taxation standpoint. The head of state, Sh. Mirziyoyev noted that more than 120 new rules will be incorporated into our nation's tax system as of January 1, 2020⁶; these rules must be correctly applied, and everyone must be aware of the changes in order to protect the rights and interests of the populace, and by understanding the fundamental principles of the tax code, it will be possible to ensure that it is implemented in a way that is both effective and compliant with the new code.

It seems appropriate to suggest that concepts like realistic resource planning, ensuring the independence of the Ombudsmen, and supporting the Government's overall reporting system to the Ombudsman be regarded as important elements. This is because the tasks facing the Business Ombudsman of Uzbekistan in many respects cannot be compared with the tasks brought on by a significantly different business climate in the countries considered in this study. The Institute of Business Ombudsman's present operations appear to fully achieve their goals and objectives. Its objectives include more than just responding to complaints; they also include eradicating the root causes of entrepreneur rights violations, resolving institutional issues in light of a broadly consolidated civil society, and actively engaging in the practical activities of the institute.

First and foremost, there is the issue of the Commissioner's resources being outstripped by the volume of complaints regarding infringements on business owners' rights. We need to find strategies to enhance resources and decrease the number of violations of entrepreneurs' rights in order to address this problem. Giving business groups the chance to handle some of the duties associated with defending the rights of entrepreneurs is one way to increase resources. In addition to handling the majority of the work on complaints based on a suitable agreement with The Ombudsman, they can send complaints they receive to the Commissioner for action. These organizations can also be officially acknowledged as partners at the same time.

Due to the fact that the remaining work has already been completed, the Ombudsman and cases on complaints that have been presented by them to the Ombudsman will be able to be evaluated quickly. The Ombudsman must contribute to raising risks and threats against dishonest government employees in order to decrease the amount of infringement of the rights of business owners. To do this, it is vital to use legal authority to bolster law enforcement efforts against them.

The Ombudsman is pursuing serious sanctions for the violations of entrepreneurs' rights that have been made public. On the other hand, harsher regulations must be introduced to punish dishonest officials who abuse their positions by, for example, publicly submitting an annual

⁵ Irbagiev H.R. Innovative ability of small and medium prepositions //Economics, 2018. № 6 (38)

⁶ Ruzinazarov, S. N., & Achilova, L. I. (2021). A new stage in the development of the civil code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of digital reality. *International Relations: Politics, Economics, Law*, 2020(1), 58-65.;

report to the President. Additionally, the promotion of such actions Deputy teams that are willing to work with the Ombudsman can carry it out.

More expert and analytical approaches must be used, together with independent research, surveys, and analytical breakthroughs, in order to eradicate the root causes of infringements on an entrepreneur's rights. One of the steps to institutionalize such contact could be the creation of a single electronic discussion forum. Through such a forum, regional commissioners, staff members, lawyers, and specialists can talk about how the ombudsmen's powers are being used, as well as share their experiences in defending the rights of business owners.

The actions of the Ombudsman are now attracting the attention of many specialists who participate in various councils and meetings, but these activities are confined to this; there is no in-depth analysis of the suggestions backed by such brainstorming sessions that is adequate to their significance.

It should be remembered that the business community, public institutions, and expert organizations that participate in the commissioners' activities ensure their authority. Their extensive involvement enhances the quality of work on the consideration of appeals and, generally, increases the credibility of the institution on the part of civil society. It also helps to shift public perception and improve the business environment. Additionally, ombudsmen's perspective, as well as their familiarity with high ideals and institutional standards, are significantly influenced by international collaboration as a source of knowledge and information. The level of expertise of the Ombudsman is greatly raised by knowledge of international best practices in defending business rights and thwarting corruption.

At the regional level, it is crucial to continue involving public organizations in the work of the Institute of Ombudsmen. Working with regional affiliates of the biggest business associations is just one aspect of this; other business associations at the regional, local, and industrial levels are also involved. Given the high level of expertise of several reputable regional institutions and expert groups, strengthening interactions with the local expert community is quite beneficial. As a result of this collaboration, severe systemic challenges will be taken into consideration while developing effective response strategies.

The Ombudsman's work includes encouraging business owners to adopt a stronger legal culture, oppose corruption, and participate in organized business community events.

Based on this, we can conclude that, by studying foreign experience, we cannot apply, that is, copy the systems of other countries, we must apply new systems based on our requirements, from our legal systems. If applicable, these conditions in our country can be used gradually, but not in a fast way. Also, ensuring the wide participation of business entities and collective organizations, as well as international organizations in the activities of business ombudsmen greatly contributes to the prosperity of business in our country.

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